

Youth Policy and Employment: National and International Experience

Abdunazarov Abdulkhay

School counselor of the Presidential school in Nurafshon in Uzbekistan

Feruza To'laganova

Deputy director for Spirituality of the Presidential school in Nurafshon in Uzbekistan

Shahlo Xatamova

Human resource manager of the Presidential school in Nurafshon in Uzbekistan

Article information:

Manuscript received: 4 Sep 2024; **Accepted:** 10 Oct 2024; **Published:** 22 Nov 2024

Abstract: Young people are the most important labor and economic potential of the society and are related to its consistent development. Today, it can be argued that a new generation has been formed in the republic. State youth policy is a driving force in unifying the efforts of various youth state and non-state organizations, creating legal, economic and organizational conditions and guarantees for the self-awareness of a young person and the development of youth associations and movements.

Keywords: Human rights, reforms, youth, UN, UNICEF.

Today, the state policy on youth is being implemented through the implementation of the target program "A perfect generation - the basis of Uzbekistan's development". It includes solving problems of interest to young people: education, work, recreation, housing for young families. The program envisages solving the problems of forming a legislative and regulatory framework, developing and gradually introducing a system of long-term lending and other financial assistance for youth education and housing construction. In addition, a system of bodies dealing with youth employment, development and support of youth entrepreneurship has been developed. At the same time, special attention is paid to the system of educational centers for the support and development of various forms of artistic creativity of young people, the creation of conditions for the spiritual and moral education of citizenship and patriotism, their training and retraining, being directed. youth workers. In recent years, youth organizations have become a truly wide field for realizing the enormous intellectual and creative potential, spiritual energy and creative spirit of the young generation. The youth policy of the state activates the creative activities of various public organizations, which is expressed in the holding of contests and examinations of pupils and students in all regions of the country. The creative enthusiasm of young people is manifested in debates between pupils and students held in secondary schools, lyceums, colleges and universities. It should be noted that in Uzbekistan there is a huge tension in the intellectual socio-cultural process, that is, in the educational and creative impulse of young people, which reveals the unexplored areas of the spiritual potential of young people. The ultimate goal of this process is to comprehensively prepare young people for life and independent development who can resist various ideological

influences and solve life problems.

For the first time in the history of the sovereign country, the National Strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Human Rights, which provides for the implementation of 78 specific measures, was adopted. They are closely related to the achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals until 2030, Uzbekistan's entry into the top 50 countries in the world in terms of international ratings and indicators in the field of human rights and freedoms, and others. National institutions for the protection of human rights - the Ombudsman institution in the parliament - NCHR have been significantly strengthened, the institutions of children and business ombudsman have been restored. Most importantly, rapid reforms are changing people's lives, worldviews and lifestyles. The people of the country gather around the new idea of "Society as the initiator of reforms" and feel a sense of belonging to the ongoing fundamental changes. The society formed a noble goal: "We will build a new Uzbekistan together."¹

Systematic measures are being implemented to raise a mature and healthy young generation, to create all conditions for it to enter an independent life. The Law "On State Policy Regarding Youth", more than 30 regulatory legal documents aimed at supporting entrepreneurial activities and initiatives of youth and youth organizations were adopted. June 30 is widely celebrated as Youth Day in Uzbekistan. Five important initiatives of the President, including widely involving young people in culture, art, physical education and sports, increasing their literacy in information technologies, promoting reading among young people and ensuring employment of women, have been implemented. is increasing. The state attaches great importance to supporting the initiatives of youth and civil institutions, the "Brave Boy" State Award, the "Builder of the Future" medal and a new badge "For the Protection of Human Rights" were established. The Youth Union of Uzbekistan, which unites more than 7,690,000 members in its ranks, was established. In Uzbekistan, the Agency for Work with Youth was established in order to raise the state policy regarding youth to a new level, to develop effective solutions to problems in the field of youth, to effectively organize and coordinate the activities of competent bodies.

We will give an illustrative example from the history of the youth policy of a state highly rated by the world community. According to the results of the elections held in 2019, nine young men and women (six percent of the total number of deputies) were elected to the Legislative Chamber. Also, young people make up almost 10 percent of the newly elected deputies of local councils. According to the estimates of the Inter-Parliamentary Union, this figure is about two percent. This is considered a positive experience in Uzbekistan, where about 60 percent of the population are young people and children. Uzbekistan believes in youth not only in the future, but also today. The establishment of the Youth Parliament under the chambers of the Oliy Majlis is a proof of this. Uzbekistan is at an important demographic threshold. Young people under 30 make up 60 percent of the population. In the next twenty years, today's children and youth will become the largest workforce in the history of Uzbekistan.² Today, with the right investments in the development of young people, they can become the generation that will lead Uzbekistan to a new stage of socio-economic development. Otherwise, not spending enough money on the well-being of today's youth can lead to disenfranchisement and high youth unemployment. This, in turn, can create grounds for political and religious extremism and increase labor emigration, leading to the loss of the precious "demographic dividend".

Our president and government are paying special attention to supporting young people and

¹<https://uza.uz/ru/posts/mezhdunarodnoe-priznanie-i-podderzhka-initsiativ-prezidenta--11-08-2020>

² <https://uzbekistan.ureport.in/>

creating opportunities for them to realize themselves and contribute to the future prosperity of their country. UNICEF supports our Government to ensure that ongoing reforms and initiatives reflect the rights, interests and aspirations of children and young people. No young man should be neglected.

UNICEF is co-chair of the UN Group on the Development of the Joint UN Youth Programme. Given the alarming number of young people working outside of work, education or training, the Joint UN Youth Program aims to empower and empower these young people. Through its programs, UNICEF not only serves young people, but also gives them voice, opportunity, and meaningful participation in the social, political, and economic life of their communities. Together with the Youth Union of the Republic of Uzbekistan, UNICEF ensures that young people are heard by the government. Voices of young people are collected through a national survey on national aspirations, needs and risks, regional youth meetings with representatives of local authorities and the innovative real-time digital platform "U-Report". The aim of the national youth survey is to examine the aspirations, needs and risks of young people from a young person's perspective on issues that affect their well-being and their ability to exercise their rights. The results of the research serve as an informative basis for the improvement and implementation of youth policy. The target audience of the research is young people between the ages of 14 and 30, including all regions of the country and all groups of the population.³ Taking into account the unique characteristics of constructive youth engagement, research methodology and tools are national partners, including the Youth Alliance, the National Movement for Uplift, the Ministry of Employment and Labor Relations, the Ministry of Public Education and the Ministry of Health.

One of the main problems of today's labor market is the increase in unemployment among young people and the poor quality of jobs given to young people. The number of unemployed youth between the ages of 15 and 24 has been steadily increasing over the past decade. In addition, hundreds of millions of young people are employed, but still live in poverty. Today, young people make up half of all unemployed people in the world. This trend is especially evident in countries where young people make up a large part of the labor force. Young people face various problems in entering the labor market. Countries in the region share some of these challenges. The global economic crisis has exacerbated the already difficult situation that has emerged in the labor markets of young people in countries. As a result of the crisis, the unemployment rate among young people has increased significantly. The unemployment rate among young people in the region has risen sharply - from 17.0% in 2008 to 20.4% in 2009, the unemployment rate has begun to decline, but has not yet returned to pre-crisis levels and is projected to reach 18 by 2018. slightly exceeds the percentage.⁴ Unemployment and underemployment have long-term negative consequences for young people. This includes the deterioration of skills and dissatisfaction. The consequences of this on the labor market can be long-term. It also has a painful impact on wages, which can delay wages for several years. In addition, youth unemployment and inactivity can lead to social exclusion, as not being able to find a job creates futility and hopelessness. Social rejection and feelings of injustice can lead to hostility and antisocial behavior.

In addition, young people in the region work mainly in the informal economy. The majority of young people working in the informal sector are in agriculture, construction and services. The large number of young workers employed in the informal economy is indicative of the low quality of youth work in these countries, as many young workers do not have access to basic labor rights, employment contracts and social protection measures. Young workers, more than other groups of workers, are engaged in low-quality, unstable types of work.

³ <https://www.unicef.org/uzbekistan>

⁴ <https://sustainabledevelopment.un.org/content/documents>

Another problem common to countries in the subregion is the mismatch of skills with labor market requirements. We can think of it as the ratio between education level and unemployment, where the higher the education level, the lower the youth unemployment rate for the region. Nevertheless, the problem of educated unemployed youth creates more serious situations. On the one hand, there are not enough jobs for young university graduates. On the other hand, there is a high and unmet demand for technicians at all skill levels. Reforming the youth policy and employment policy, using the experience of successful countries to train qualified specialists with the latest technologies, but also to ensure their competitiveness in the labor market, increase the rate of economic growth, but the decrease in youth unemployment, youth unemployment, in our opinion, as a socio-economic phenomenon, means that economically active young people are ready to work, but it can also be observed that they are not employed in the production of goods and services.⁵ This type of unemployment leads to the fact that the most enterprising, educated, active part of the population, after graduating from an educational institution, is forced to take the status of unemployed. For the majority of young people, the state of unemployment means not only a decrease in the standard of living, but also a serious psychological injury to a person, the inability to provide themselves with the necessary life resources.

It is known that neglecting youth unemployment not only creates a sense of social security and uselessness among young people, but also gives an irreparable blow to the state economy. According to the International Labor Organization, a reduction in youth unemployment and maximum youth employment in the world of work would almost double GDP growth. Often, the problem of youth employment is the lack of coordination between universities that train specialists of different profiles with the needs of the labor market, which also leads to an increase in unemployment among graduates of vocational education institutions, among young people. Unemployment is not only an economic but also a social and status issue of survival, which affects young people most directly and strongly.

The situation of young people in the framework of the employment policy, which is also responsible for the employment of graduates, is somewhat different in European countries. The experience of implementing the main provisions of the youth employment policy does not mean that it has been able to overcome the unemployment problems without words, but what the governments are doing can be a good example for conducting the youth employment policy of Russia. Expertise and financial support for youth projects and programs are regularly implemented at the municipal level.

Used literature and sources

1. <https://uza.uz>
2. <https://www.unicef.org>
3. <https://sustainabledevelopment.un.org>
4. <https://uzbekistan.ureport.in/>
5. <http://www.mpa-sf.ru>

⁵ Федеральный закон о молодежи и молодежной политике: аргументы "за" [Электронный ресурс]. URL: <http://www.mpa-sf.ru/news/308--lr.html>